

www.bjisrd.com

Translation Strategies of Literary Text

Azatova Nodira Anvarbek kizi

Teacher of the Faculty of Foreign Philology, Urgench State University,

Yuldosheva Mahliyo Komiljon kizi

2nd year student of the Faculty of Foreign Philology, Urgench State University

Abstract: This article discusses the morphological, syntactic, lexicological and methodological problems that arise in the process of translation, including the etymology and history of the term translation, its main types and strategies. The topic is covered in a practical and theoretical way with several scholars who have contributed to translation studies and their views on translation strategies. Basic translation strategies are illustrated with examples. In particular, several examples of comparative and contrastive translations are given.

Key words: Norms, morphology, style, syntax, lexicology, term, factor, consecutive translation, visual translation, simultaneous translation, tarzabon, text segment, syntagmatic.

Translating any text from its native language to another language is not as easy as it seems. In today's era of global communication, a translator who acts as a bridge between two languages in the process of communication between languages must first of all be familiar not only with that foreign language, but also with its history, culture, way of life and religion, only it is necessary to have thoroughly studied the phrases and language units belonging to that nation. Only then, the translation process can be easier than expected. How the translator solves the problems that arise during the translation and how to deliver it without losing the stability of the meaning in the text are called translation strategies in the science. Different scholars have looked at the aspects of the act of translation in different ways and have explained several strategies based on this. In particular, as noted by Lorsch [1], the concept of translation strategies is rarely found in translation theory and is not clearly defined. According to Lorsch: "A translation strategy is a conscious process of translating a problem faced by an individual, that is, a text segment from one language to another." Hejvovski [2] includes "surface strategy", "situation frame selection strategy", "scenario strategy" and "schema strategy" as the main translation strategies. According to Hejvovski, the surface strategy (called syntagmatic) is based on the automatic knowledge of the corresponding surface structures of two languages. This strategy allows people to translate texts and parts of them that they do not fully understand. Scenario strategy is based on knowledge of the usual

sequence of events and actions. Its application usually requires some knowledge of the lifestyles and realities of both cultures. In today's rapidly developing life, we cannot imagine mutual political, economic, scientific and cultural cooperation between nations without language and translation. Professor, translation scholar Gaybulla Salomov [3] did not point out for nothing that "Ignorance of the life of other peoples leads to ignorance and national limitations." For this reason, we can consider translation as a bridge between nations.

Let's turn to the history of the origin of the word "interpreter". In ancient times, the art of oratory was widely developed among the peoples of Central Asia and Iran. Speakers were called "Tarzabon". "Tar" means "fresh", "juicy", "gentle", "delicate" in Persian. "Zaban" means "language". Tarzaban means eloquent, one who says beautiful words, master of words. In addition to having deep knowledge and the art of eloquence, they also knew several languages and used them in their speeches. After the Arab invasion, social life, culture, science and other areas were also influenced by them, and many words were assimilated and pronounced according to the rules of the Arabic language. In particular, the word tarzaban has also changed in pronunciation to "interpreter" or "interpreter". Translation comes from the word translator. "The process of converting an idea or text from one language to another in a specific language orally or in writing is called translation" [4]. The meaning of the concept of translation is very broad. In this process, scientific, scientific-popular books, diplomatic documents, official papers, various newspaper and magazine articles and similar sources are used in this process. For this reason, it is important for the translator to have sufficient knowledge of various fields and a broad worldview. The establishment of the International Association of Translators in 1953 was also of great importance to all those interested in the field.

In the process of intercultural translation, translators can use several strategies. We can distinguish the following types of translation: consecutive translation, visual translation and simultaneous translation. Consecutive translation is the translation of oral information in one language into another language. The translator translates in a concise form, understanding the generality of the speaker's speech. There are 3 principles of this translation method: comprehension, analysis and re-expression. Visual translation means reading a text written in one language translated into another language, and this type of translation is relatively easier. In simultaneous translation, the interpreter sits in a room reserved for translation and listens to the speaker using special headphones and translates through a microphone. Delegates in the conference room listen to the main language through headphones. This type is more complex and responsible than the above. Because in this process, the translator is required to translate quickly and without skipping a beat and to master the language perfectly.

In this article, we will talk about a number of syntactic, lexicological and methodological problems and their norms that may arise in the translation of literary texts.

1. Morphological norms: Morphological norms are based on the structure of words in sentences and texts and their connection with other parts of speech. For example: *Men bugun dars qilmadim*, the word groups are proportionally connected in the phrase. Unlike English, Uzbek has a different order of words in a sentence. In English, the possessive comes first, followed by the participle and the rest of the

clauses after that, while in Uzbek, the participle comes at the end of the sentence as the closing part of the sentence. *I didn't do my homework today.*

2. Syntactic norms: Syntactic norms are based on the connection of words in a sentence, word combinations and types of sentences. In this case, the fragments are mainly connected in terms of meaning and grammar. *The hallway smelt of boiled cabbage and old rag mats* [5]. In this sentence, possessive and participle (the hallway smelt), as well as demonstrative determiners (boiled cabbage and old rag mats) are connected in terms of meaning and grammar.

3. Lexicological standards: This standard is based on the subtleties of meaning of words, synonyms, antonyms, phrases and phraseological units. And in my opinion, the lexicological elements are the primary factor in the translation process of the literary text. Because the extent to which the author's opinion reaches the listener and reader depends on the skill of the translator. For example: *I felt blue when my application for Harvard had been rejected*, in the sentence FEEL BLUE does not mean "Feeling blue", or "Bluish", but "Being upset", Means "offense". In this case, it would be appropriate if our sentence is translated as "I was very disappointed when I was not accepted to Harvard University." There are many examples of such phrases, the important thing is to deliver them correctly and accurately.

4. Stylistic norms: In stylistic norms, the main factor is the use of a word in which contexts of conversation and in relation to whom. In this case, a suitable word is chosen according to the formality or informality of the conversation. It should be noted that it is not recommended to translate word-for-word in the process of translation (of course there are exceptions). For example: the expression Dressed to kill appears in literal translation as "Dressed to kill". But if we see it in context, a completely different meaning emerges: *Sheila invited us to her birthday party and there were girls all dressed to kill*. No one should dress to kill for a party?! That is, this phrase is translated as "dressed with horror", "carrying". As you can see, the context plays an important role in understanding the meaning of a phrase.

In the translation of a literary text, first of all, it is recommended to study the culture, language, history, lifestyle, religion, politics, economy, let's say the whole existence of this people. Only then the translator can convey the correct information to the reader and reader. The above-mentioned factors are, of course, part of the dough. The translator needs to be intelligent and have deep thoughts in order to complete the translation. In particular, our great ancestor Alisher Navoi "Zullisonayn", the sultan of the ghazal estate, was considered a creator. Zullisayn - perfect knowledge of two languages or a specific literary language and its dialect. This tradition may have been due to compulsion or social demand. In other words, the main factor was the close living of 2 or more nationalities in the territory of one country. Along with his mother tongue, Navoi also mastered the Persian language perfectly. He collected his works written in this language in the collection "Devoni Foni". Writers who create in two languages can be found even now. In particular, the famous Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov also writes freely in Kyrgyz and Russian languages. In general, bilingualism as a social phenomenon is an important factor influencing the enrichment and development of languages and the increase of the universal cultural level [6].

In this respect, mastering not only two languages, but even more, opens up wide paths at the international level and creates a basis for close study of peoples and nations. As mentioned above, the

field of translation serves as a strong and unbreakable bridge between nations and peoples. In order to eliminate any problem that may arise in this process and achieve a clean and accurate result, it is appropriate for the translator to use not only the grammar and literature of the language being translated, but also the careful translation strategies that are available during the process. After all, work without a plan does not show the expected result. It should be noted that the translation process and the translation of literary texts require more work and creativity from the translator than from the speaker and the author of the work. Because the author pours all the ideas in his imagination directly on paper. A translator is not a soothsayer who can know exactly what is being expressed by these words. Here he is faced with the difficulty of choosing words, sentences, proverbs and equivalents that are suitable for expressions, and he has to choose options depending on the situation. It is precisely in this process that the theoretical and practical knowledge, creative skills, which are carefully acquired, can lead the translator out of this precipice. That is why the need for the art of re-creating an artistic text will never disappear and will be refined and enriched over the years.

The artistic text strategies mentioned in this article are the result of personal views and studies. How to understand and apply them depends on the discretion and skill of the translator.

The list of used literature:

1. Lörcher, W. The translation process: Methods and problems of its investigation. *Meta*, 50 (2), (1991).
2. Hejvovski, K. Kognitywno-komunikacyjna teoria przekladu [The cognitive-communicative theory of translation]. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN. (2004).
3. G'aybulla Salomov. "Tarjima nazariyasiga kirish". Toshkent: "O'qituvchi", 1978.
4. E.Ochilov. Tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyoti (o'quv qo'llanmasi). Toshkent-2012. 7-bet.
5. George Orwell, "Nineteen Eighty-four (1984)". Harcourt Brace & Co. 1949, page-3
6. O'zME. Birinchi jild. Toshkent, 2000-yil.